

Effect of late planting and lopping on productivity of traditional tall basmati rice

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Among several high-quality aromatic/scented rice varieties grown in India, traditional tall basmati varieties are continuously being threatened by high-yielding cultivars. They are now considered endangered cultivars. The main reason for the genetic erosion is their low productivity, which is mainly attributed to severe lodging and poor response to nitrogen. If efforts are not made to improve their productivity and to preserve them, they may become extinct very soon.

In improving their productivity, their genetic makeup must not be altered. Agrophysiological manipulation is thus indispensable and is perhaps the only viable biological approach to conserve these precious genetic resources. Using two traditional tall basmati rice cultivars, Basmati 370 and Karnal Local, a field experiment was carried out to improve grain yield without genetic manipulation.

The trial was conducted at the IARI research farm during the 1998 and 1999 wet seasons. The field was divided into three blocks, each divided further into six plots to accommodate three treatments: normal planting (T1), late planting (T2), and lopping (cutting of foliage) (T3). The field was fertilized with a full dose of P and K at 40 and 30 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, before planting. Under normal-planting and lopping treatments, 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted in mid-July, whereas under the late-planting treatment, transplanting was delayed by a month (i.e., in mid-August) with seedlings used for normal planting (60 d old). All plots received a full dose of 50 kg N ha⁻¹ 1 wk after transplanting. Lopping was done from 40–50 cm above the ground at panicle initiation stage to reduce the luxurious vegetative growth of shoots, which is responsible for lodging.

Results show that both lopping and late planting improved the productivity of both cultivars, but the extent of improvement was significantly higher in Basmati 370 than in Karnal Local (see table). Agrophysiological manipulation, such as lopping and late planting, caused a marked reduction in height and vegetative shoot growth, which in turn reduced the extent of lodging and eventually resulted in higher productivity. The number of tillers m⁻², grains panicle⁻¹, and harvest index were increased. Lodging is considered the

main biological constraint to sink potential realization in traditional tall rice cultivars. Despite the significant reduction in biological yield by nongenetic manipulation, the marked increase in grain yield was mainly attributed to a significant improvement in harvest index. Irrespective of treatments, Basmati 370 had better yield and yield-attributing characters than Karnal Local. Thus, agrophysiological manipulation improved the productivity of these basmati rice varieties without any effect on grain and cooking quality characteristics.

Growth, yield, and yield components of basmati rice cultivars as influenced by late planting and lopping.

Variety/ treatment	Plant height (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	1,000- grain wt (g)	Economic yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Straw yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Biological yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Harvest index (%)
<i>1998 wet season</i>								
Basmati 370								
Normal	170	405	35	24.0	3.2	11.8	15.0	21
Late planting	152	412	45	24.5	4.1	8.4	12.5	33
Lopping	155	410	50	23.8	3.9	8.1	12.0	32
Karnal Local								
Normal	175	390	30	23.5	2.5	12.0	14.5	17
Late planting	156	415	40	23.2	3.2	9.8	13.0	24
Lopping	165	406	35	23.3	2.8	8.7	11.5	24
LSD (5%)								
Variety (V)	ns	ns	3	ns ^a	0.5	ns	1.3	4
Treatment (T)	12	15	5	ns	0.8	3.1	3.0	7
V × T	16	17	9	ns	1.1	3.8	3.5	10
<i>1999 wet season</i>								
Basmati 370								
Normal	165	400	40	24.0	3.8	13.2	17.0	22
Late planting	145	410	50	24.2	4.8	8.8	13.6	35
Lopping	150	405	58	24.5	4.5	8.5	13.0	35
Karnal Local								
Normal	170	385	35	23.0	2.8	13.2	16.0	18
Late planting	150	415	52	23.5	3.5	10.5	14.0	25
Lopping	160	400	50	23.5	3.0	7.0	10.0	30
LSD (5%)								
Variety (V)	ns	ns	4	ns	0.5	ns	1.1	5
Treatment (T)	10	12	6	ns	0.7	2.5	2.8	8
V × T	15	16	10	ns	1.0	3.2	3.5	10

^ans = nonsignificant.